

A Hybrid Add-on Damping Strategy for Self-Stabilization Nanopositioning System with High-Static-Low-Dynamic Stiffness Property

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Abstract—The inspection of micro/mini light-emitting diode (LED) display panels using industrial-level atomic force microscopes (AFM scanning head) demands a vibration isolator with high-ratio vibration reduction and high-precision positioning, in the presence of complex environmental disturbances. The motivation of this paper is to combine the ability of passive and active damping methods to enhance the vibration isolation performance of the developed compliant self-stabilization system to further improve the inspection performance. This objective is achieved by modifying the system with a hybrid add-on damping (HAD) strategy that improves the vibration isolation in the resonant region. First, based on the analysis of the system, a HAD strategy is proposed to address the limitations of the passive-active vibration isolation strategy. Then, the design, modeling, and optimization of a flexure-based high-static-low-dynamics stiffness mechanism (FHSM) are demonstrated, which dampens the system without deteriorating the high-frequency transmissibility. Besides, an active bandwidth-limited damper (ABD) is developed to further enhance damping in the desired frequency range. Finally, a series of verification tests were conducted, including performance tests of vibration isolation and closed-loop positioning. The experimental results indicate that from 1 Hz to 500 Hz, the vibration reduction ratio is achieved as 91% in the resonant region and over 94.5% in other frequencies. Besides, the steady-state positioning error is within $\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ with a 2.5 kg load capacity. All the results uniformly confirm that the proposed HAD has successfully damped the system to achieve a higher vibration reduction ratio.

Index Terms—Flexure, atomic force microscope (AFM) scanning head, compliant mechanism, hybrid add-on damping strategy (HAD), vibration isolation.

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Fig. 1. Diagram of an ultra-HD display panel surface inspection system with AFM scanning head. (a) The overall system. (b) The detail of vibration isolator. (c) Vibration isolation for AFM scanning head. (d) AFM images with and without the vibration isolator.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the “ultra-HD display era”, micro/mini LED chips have emerged and gained extensive utilization in display panels, due to their exceptional performance in terms of high dynamic range, slim profile, and low power consumption [1]. To ensure a high yield rate ($> 99.99\%$), a device that offers high-precision inspection of 3-D surface physical properties is essential [2], [3], which presents opportunities for the industrial application of AFM systems. To enable the AFM system to inspect the large display panel (workplace ≥ 1 m) with high efficiency, a solution is that the AFM scanning head is fixed on the gantry and moved by macro motion stage, as shown in Fig.1(a). Due to the unique operational principle, it is significant to ensure the stability and reliability of the AFM inspection system. To this end, a vibration isolator is essential to dampen the vibrations transmitted from the motion stage on the gantry to the AFM scanning head, as shown in Fig.1(b). The isolator needs to guarantee both positioning accuracy of AFM and high vibration reduction simultaneously, as illustrated in Fig.1(c). With this effort, a high-precision inspection of large LED display panel can be achieved, as shown in Fig.1(d).

To cater for this requirement, our previous work [4] developed a compliant self-stabilization system with a modified active-passive hybrid vibration isolation strategy based on flexure-based nanopositioning technology. The system addresses this issue by combining the ability of piezo-actuator (PZT) in terms of high resolution, large force, and no friction

[5]–[7], with the capabilities of voice coil motors (VCM) including high power and fast speed [8]. However, the system suffered from the inherent dynamics of lightly damping resonance, resulting in a lower vibration reduction ratio in the resonant region. Even worse, the large flexure used to decrease the natural frequency makes it difficult to handle the resonance effectively. In result, the transmissibility in the resonant region is close to 0 dB, indicating that no vibration attenuation. Therefore, the resonant frequency of the system must be placed at the location with minimal disturbances, which greatly limits its applicability.

To deal with the aforementioned problem, the system can be damped to suppress the resonant peak, thus the vibration at that frequency can be effectively attenuated. The passive damping approaches are demonstrated as effective methods to dampen the resonant mode, which works by absorbing and decaying the energy from resonance by a mechanical device, such as damped flexure hinge [9], [10], quasi-zero-stiffness mechanism [11], [12], and metastructure [13], [14]. Different from passive damper, active damping method suppresses the vibration by designing a control strategy for the actuator to achieve high-precision isolation, including positive position feedback control [15], [16], disturbance observer-based control [17], [18], and integral resonant control [19], [20]. However, when attempting to achieve system damping for high vibration reduction ration within large working range, they encounter the issue of implementation. The passive damping suppresses the resonant peak but increases the amplification of high-frequency transmissibility. To this end, it becomes imperative to introduce damping not only for resonant mode but also for high order modes. On the other hand, to enable high-performance active damping, an actuator that offers large force is essential. To achieve the above modification, the solution often involves incorporating a large and heavy damper into the system. Nevertheless, achieving such dampers by upgrading the working modules of the developed system presents challenges in terms of availability, difficulty, and cost in practice.

To this end, a HAD strategy is proposed in this work, integrating the capability of passive and active damping methods. Based on stiffness recomposition, a FHSM is designed as an add-on passive damper to pre-dampen the system by high-static-low-dynamic stiffness property. Then, to further dampen the resonant mode in a desired frequency range, an ABD is developed as an add-on active damper, which is designed by a proposed tuning objective. Thanks to the system pre-damping of FHSM, the ABD can be implemented by working as low authority control and sharing the actuator of the original system. Finally, a set of experiments was successfully fulfilled and confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed HAD strategy.

The main contribution of this work is to propose a HAD strategy to enhance the vibration isolation performance of the developed self-stabilization nanopositioning system, which achieves by suppressing the resonant peak of the vibration isolator with reducing the deterioration of high-frequency transmissibility and can be flexibly implemented in various high-precision end-effectors. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this work is the first attempt at enhancing the performance of hybrid vibration isolators via the high-static-low-dynamic

Fig. 2. Problems of compliant self-stabilization system. (a) Dynamics model of the system. (b) Effect of low-frequency resonance of the system. (c) Limitation of increasing c_p .

stiffness property from a new viewpoint. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: the problem of compliant self-stabilization system and the proposed HAD are illustrated in section II; in section III, the mechanical design and modeling of FHSM is presented; the control strategy including the ABD is demonstrated in section IV; in section V, a set of validation experiments and performance evaluations are stated. Finally, section VI provides a conclusion for this paper.

II. HYBRID ADD-ON DAMPING STRATEGY

In this section, the problem of the developed compliant self-stabilization system is first presented, followed by description of the HAD strategy.

A. Problem statement of compliant self-stabilization nanopositioning system

The compliant self-stabilization system can be divided into three parts, that is passive vibration isolator (leaf spring), active vibration isolator (PZT), and force compensator (VCM), where the details can be found in [4]. The dynamics model is shown in Fig.2(a), where the vibration acts on the gantry from the top side. A pair of PZTs force the active vibration isolator to reject the vibration as a disturbance in the control bandwidth and ensure the positioning accuracy, thereafter the high-frequency vibration is attenuated by the passive vibration isolator, which is connected to the AFM scanning head rigidly. Besides, a VCM acts on the AFM scanning head as the force compensator. With the above analysis, the dynamics equation of the system can be derived as follows:

$$-m_p \ddot{x}_p + c_p (\dot{x}_a - \dot{x}_p) + k_p (x_a - x_p) = F_V \quad (1)$$

where m_p , k_p and c_p are the mass, stiffness, and damping factor of the passive vibration isolator, respectively. The states x_p and x_a represent the displacement of passive and active vibration isolator, respectively. The input force of VCM is denoted as F_V . With the Laplace transformation of (1) for free vibration, the transfer function of transmissibility of passive vibration isolator can be obtained:

$$Tr(s) = \frac{X_a(s)}{X_p(s)} = \frac{c_p s + k_p}{m_p s^2 + c_p s + k_p} \quad (2)$$

Based on (2), the transmissibility is plotted in Fig.2(b). It can be observed that a sharp resonant peak is located in low frequency, due to the lightly damping resonance behavior of

Fig. 3. 3-D diagram of the compliant self-stabilization nanopositioning system. (a) Assembly diagram including (1) AFM scanning head, (2) Passive isolator (leaf spring), (3) active isolator (PZT), (4) preload spring, (5) flexure-based high-static-low-dynamics stiffness mechanism, and (6) active bandwidth-limited damper (VCM actuator). (b) Dynamics model of HAD strategy.

the flexure-based leaf spring. In result, a high control effort at the resonant frequency is needed to stabilize the system, denoted as the sensitive function $S(s)$ with low amplitude as shown in Fig.2(b). According to the Bode's sensitivity integral constraints, a high control bandwidth is required to obtain low amplitude of $S(s)$ in the resonant region. However, due to the broadband noise in the environment in Fig.R1(c), it is necessary to limit the control bandwidth to ensure that the system becomes insensitive to this noise. Therefore, it is difficult to effectively suppress the resonant peak by the active control method in this work. For passive damping methods, although it can provide robust damping effort on the system, the transmissibility in high-frequency range will be increased, while the vibration in that frequency range is suppressed by the passive isolator mainly, as shown in Fig.2(c). As a result, the performance of vibration isolation in high-frequency range will be degraded, thus the working range of the developed system is decreased. In a word, the current damping methods are hard to achieve high-efficiency resonant peak suppressing and large working range, simultaneously. Finally, limited by the sharp resonant peak, the performance is restricted as the vibration is almost 100 % transmitted onto the AFM scanning head, that is $|Tr(\omega_s)| \approx 1$. This restriction presented a challenge in designing and fine-tuning the compliant self-stabilization system to meet the requirements.

B. Description of hybrid add-on damping strategy

Here, the proposed HAD is presented, which is added to the compliant self-stabilization system. The modified system is displayed as shown in Fig.3(a), where the AFM scanning head is fixed on the passive isolator, and its motion is compensated by the active vibration isolator and VCM actuator, where the VCM is worked as an ABD in this paper instead of force compensator. Two FHSMs are inserted into the passive vibration isolator by two brackets to dampen the system. Besides, a pair of preload springs connect the gantry and AFM scanning head. The dynamics model of the system after introducing HAD is shown in Fig.3(b). For implementation, a capacitive displacement sensor is first attached to measure the position of end-effector to obtain the offset in real-time. Then, the preload spring is adjusted to reserve installation space for

Fig. 4. Stiffness transformation of the FHSM. (a) Added FHSM. (b) Stiffness decomposition. (c) Stiffness recomposition.

Fig. 5. Low-frequency vibration suppression by the HAD. (a) With FHSM. (b) With ABD.

the FHSM, by increasing the stiffness of the spring. Next, a bracket is fixed on the active isolator to support the FHSM, followed by inserting the FHSM between the end-effector and the bracket. Finally, adjust the preload spring by decreasing the stiffness, until the offset of the end-effector is eliminated. In a word, the HAD strategy can be implemented via a set of components attached to the system with the advantages of compact space, thus it can be easily achieved.

1) *Flexure-based high-static-low-dynamics stiffness mechanism*: Here, the working mode of FHSM is introduced, which helps to understand the following analysis. The passive damper is necessary since it can effectively reduce the effort of ABD and enhance the reliability of system. The FHSM is designed by the quasi-zero-stiffness mechanism, which consists of two groups flexure beams. When payloads are added, one group of beams present positive stiffness to static payloads, while another group of beams offer negative stiffness to dynamics payloads. Thanks to the monolithic FHSM, the passive damper can be implemented in a relatively flexible size. The details of FHSM can be found in the following Section III.

Here, the effectiveness of FHSM is analyzed in theory. With the addition of FHSM, the dynamics model of the system is illustrated as Fig.4(a), where k_z and c_z are the stiffness and damping factor of FHSM, respectively. The high-static-low-dynamics stiffness is achieved by a quasi-zero-stiffness unit, the so-called "soft spring" [21]. With this behavior, the stiffness of the original device, which is limited by the load balancing, can be further reduced thanks to the high-static add-on stiffness. In this case, the stiffness of FHSM can be decomposed as shown in Fig.4(b), and k_z is rewritten as:

$$k_z = k_z^p + k_z^n \quad (3)$$

where k_z^p and k_z^n are the positive and negative stiffness of

Fig. 6. Design of FHSM. (a) FHSM. (b) Deflection analysis of FHSM.

FHSM, respectively. According to the aforementioned low-dynamics stiffness of FHSM, the negative stiffness k_z^n can be assumed as:

$$k_z^n = \begin{cases} 0, & \omega = 0 \text{ rad/s} \\ -\bar{k}_z^n, & \omega > 0 \text{ rad/s} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $-\bar{k}_z^n$ is a constant to define the negative stiffness. By the recombination of parallel springs, the stiffness of the original passive vibration isolator can be reduced by adjusting the preload spring ($k_p \rightarrow k_{p'}$), as shown in Fig.4(c) and satisfy following equation:

$$k_{p'} + k_z^p = k_p \quad (5)$$

Combing (3), (4) and (5), the stiffness of passive vibration isolator with FHSM is derived as:

$$k_{pu} = k_{p'} + k_z^p + k_z^n = k_p + k_z^n \quad (6)$$

By (6), it can be obtained that the stiffness of passive isolator is invariant under static load, which indicates the load capacity is maintained. From (4), the stiffness of passive isolator is decreased under dynamics load. Meanwhile, the add-on damping makes $c_{pu} = c_p \rightarrow c_p + c_z$, where c_{pu} is the damping coefficient of the system after adding FHSM. Therefore, the transmissibility in high-frequency does not increase but the resonant peak is damped as shown in Fig.5(a).

2) *Active bandwidth-limited damper*: The effort of passive damper is commonly limited, due to mechanical constraints, including add-on space, manufacturing processes, and material. Hence, to further dampen the system within a controllable bandwidth, the VCM actuator is worked as an add-on ABD, which offers a velocity negative feedback in a certain frequency range. As shown in Fig.5(b), the system is damped in $[0, \omega_t]$, but this effort does not work beyond ω_t , thus it is insensitive to the high-order resonant modes and high-frequency noise. Compared to the original force compensator, the ‘‘low authority control’’ of ABD allows VCM to provide more power to dampen the resonant peak, effectively reducing the control effort of PZT on vibration rejection, while the ‘‘high authority controller’’ of tracking control strategy in previous work encountered the trade-off between steady-state accuracy and vibration rejection.

TABLE I
MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SEVERAL HIGH-STRAIN MATERIALS.

Material	Fatigue stress σ_{Fa}/MPa	E/GPa	Density $\rho/(\text{kg}/\text{m}^3)$	ε_{Fa} (σ_{Fa}/E)
Ti-6Al-4V	470	113.8	4430	0.0041
Al7075-T6	223	71.7	2810	0.0031
55Si2MnB	720	206.6	7750	0.0034
PA11	50	1.07	1040	0.0467

III. MECHANICAL DESIGN AND MODELING

A. Design of flexure-based high-static-low-dynamics stiffness mechanism

The FHSM is designed as shown in Fig.6(a), which consists of two parallel quasi-zero-stiffness units to enhance the load capacity and the rotational stiffness. In terms of a single unit, a pair of centrally-clamped cosine-shaped beams are placed on top and bottom. According to [22], the force-displacement relationship for the first three buckling modes is obtained as:

$$f_i(d) = \begin{cases} \frac{\pi^4 E I d}{2l^3 t^3} [3(d-h)(d-2h) + 4t^2], & i = 1 \\ \frac{\pi^4 E I h}{l^3} \left[4.18 - 2.18 \frac{d}{h} \right], & i = 2 \\ \frac{\pi^4 E I h}{l^3} \left[8 - 6 \frac{d}{h} \right], & i = 3 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where l , b , t , and h are the span, depth, thickness, and initial apex height of the cosine-shaped beam, respectively, as shown in Fig.6(b). Besides, $I = bt^3/12$ is the moment of inertia and E denotes the Young’s modulus. Then, $f_i(d)$ means the applied force that relates to deflection d in the i^{th} mode. With careful design, f_1 will intersect with f_3 at three points of the force-displacement curve and can be derived as:

$$\begin{cases} d_1 = h - \sqrt{9h^2 - 48t^2}/3 \\ d_2 = h \\ d_3 = h + \sqrt{9h^2 - 48t^2}/3 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where (d_1, d_2, d_3) are the stable state points of the first three modes. Substitute (8) into (7) yields:

$$f_1(d_1) = \frac{2\pi^4 E I}{l^3} \left(h + \sqrt{9h^2 - 48t^2} \right) \quad (9)$$

where $f_1(d_1)$ denotes the maximum force of the first mode, that is the largest static load.

B. Material selection

The mechanical properties of the FHSM are determined by the material, thus the material selection process is significantly important. Considering working by large deflection of negative stiffness mechanism, a high ratio of fatigue stress to Young’s modulus (ε_{Fa}) is essential to avoid fatigue and failure of the material. Furthermore, to reduce the resonant frequency of the passive vibration isolator, a low stiffness mechanism is desired,

Fig. 7. The force-displacement results of FHSM. (a) 2nd mode. (b) 3rd mode. (c) Force-displacement curve. (d) Fatigue analysis.

thus the material should be low density. The common materials with high ε_{Fa} are listed in Table I, and it can be observed that the PA11 owns higher ε_{Fa} and lower density than other materials. Therefore, the nylon PA11 is adopted as the material in this work.

C. Optimization Statement and Results

As shown in Fig.6(b), the designed parameters of FHSM are: span l , depth b , thickness t , and initial apex height h . First, a high load capacity is desired, which can be achieved by maximizing f_1 in (9). Besides, the load capacity should be lower than the weight of the AFM scanning head to ensure FHSM works within the negative stiffness region. Thereafter, the FHSM is worked in the range between 1st and 2nd modes. According to [22], a large distance between the first and second points $\Delta d = d_2 - d_1$ could generate a large negative stiffness to decrease the resonant frequency, thus low dynamics of FHSM can be obtained. This objective can be obtained by maximizing Δd by (8). Additionally, Δd should be larger than the magnitude of vibration to ensure the effectiveness of negative stiffness. Limited by the manufacturing process and installation space, the designed parameters should be restricted. With the aforementioned considerations, the optimization problem can be summarized as follows:

- 1) *objective*: maximize $f_1(d_1)$ and maximize Δd ;
- 2) *related parameters*: l , b , t , and h ;
- 3) *subject to*:
 - a) maximum static load capacity < 12.5 N;
 - b) Factor of safety (Fos) > 1.5 ;
 - c) $\Delta d \geq 12\mu\text{m}$;
 - d) ranges: $0.6\text{mm} \leq b \leq 5\text{mm}$, $0.6\text{mm} \leq t$, $h \leq 13\text{mm}$, and $l \leq 25\text{mm}$.

The optimization task was conducted by MATLAB using the Pareto method. The two objectives are all to decrease the resonant frequency of passive vibration isolator. After several iterations, the optimization dimensions are obtained as follows: $l = 22\text{mm}$, $b = 1.8\text{mm}$, $t = 0.6\text{mm}$, and $h = 9.1\text{mm}$.

Fig. 8. The modal analysis results of FHSM. (a) 1st mode with precompression. (b) 2nd mode with precompression. (c) 1st mode without precompression. (d) 2nd mode without precompression.

D. FEA and evaluation

The established models for evaluating performances of the optimized FHSM and compliant self-stabilization system in terms of force–displacement property and natural frequencies are validated by the ANSYS Workbench, respectively. The processes of static structural and modal analysis are described as follows.

In order to evaluate the force-displacement property, a displacement with ramp-shaped varying is acted on the load side of FHSM and records the reaction force. The analysis results are displayed in Fig.7(a), Fig.7(b), and Fig.7(c), indicating that the first three steady-state points are located at 1.1 mm, 6.2 mm, and 13.7 mm. Moreover, the largest force of the first mode is 17.9 N, which means that each unit is 8.5 N. It can be obtained that limited by the working space, the FHSM offers 68 % of the maximum static load capacity of the optimization objective. Besides, the minimum Fos is larger than about 1.6, as shown in Fig.7(d).

Thereafter, the modal analysis of the compliant self-stabilization system is performed in both two cases, which are achieved by using the model of FHSM in the shape of the first and second mode. The "large deflection" term in the Workbench is on, and the damping ratio is set as zero. When analyzing with precompression, the first and second of the system are 7.8 Hz and 53.3 Hz, where the mode shape of the first frequency is the vertical translation of FHSM, and the second frequency is the vertical translation of leaf spring, as shown in Fig.8(a) and Fig.8(b). In the case without precompression, the analysis results are illustrated in Fig.8(c) and Fig.8(d), where the first frequency increases to 9.4 Hz, and the second frequency is 53.3 Hz. Besides, the detail of the second modes before rounding are 53.288 Hz and 53.296 Hz, respectively. By the aforementioned results, we get FHSM decreases the first frequency of 17.7 %. The second mode is the same degree of freedom as the first, thus it can be suppressed by FHSM. Furthermore, the third mode is 85 Hz with the same mode shape as the two cases.

Fig. 9. System diagram of control strategy.

Fig. 10. Design of ABD. (a) Tuning objective (17). (b) Normalized objective (18).

E. Dynamics modeling

Here, the dynamics model of the compliant self-stabilization system with HAD is derived for control design. Based on the aforementioned analysis, the dynamics equation (1) is rewritten as:

$$m_p \ddot{x}_p = k_{pu}(x_a - x_p) + c_{pu}(\dot{x}_a - \dot{x}_p) + F_V \quad (10)$$

When considering the transmissibility from active vibration isolator to passive vibration isolator by (10), we get:

$$m_p \ddot{x}_p + k_{pu}(x_p - x_a) + c_{pu}(\dot{x}_p - \dot{x}_a) = 0 \quad (11)$$

Similarly, the transmissibility from VCM actuator to passive vibration isolator is:

$$m_p \ddot{x}_p + k_{pu}x_p + c_{pu}\dot{x}_p = F_V \quad (12)$$

After the Laplace transformation of the aforementioned equations (11) and (12), the following transfer functions are obtained:

$$\begin{cases} G_p(s) = \frac{X_p(s)}{X_a(s)} = \frac{c_{pu}s + k_{pu}}{m_p s^2 + c_{pu}s + k_{pu}} = \bar{G}(s)G(s) \\ G_V(s) = \frac{X_p(s)}{F_V(s)} = \frac{1}{m_p s^2 + c_{pu}s + k_{pu}} = G(s) \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where $G_p(s)$ and $G_V(s)$ are the transfer functions from active vibration isolator to passive vibration isolator, and VCM actuator to passive vibration isolator, respectively.

IV. CONTROL STRATEGY

The control strategy of the compliant self-stabilization system can be divided into two parts, that is a baseline tracking controller with PZT actuator, and an add-on ABD with VCM actuator as shown in Fig.9. To dampen the system within a desired control bandwidth, the controller of ABD utilizes the tamed differentiator (TD) to offer a bandwidth-limited negative feedback of the plant velocity:

$$C_{TD}(s) = K_t \frac{s}{s + \omega_t} \quad (14)$$

where K_t and ω_t are the control gain and cut-off frequency, respectively. With the addition of ABD, the plant is pre-damped:

$$G_d(s) = \frac{G(s)}{1 + C_{TD}(s)G(s)} \quad (15)$$

In terms of tuning TD, a large gain K_t can enhance control effort on system damping with control constraints. The cut-off frequency ω_t defines the damping range in the frequency domain within $[0, \omega_t]$.

The baseline controller is to reject the vibration within the control bandwidth and ensure the positioning accuracy of the AFM scanning head. The typical proportional-integral (PI) tracking controller is adopted in this work:

$$C_B(s) = K_p + K_i \frac{1}{s} \quad (16)$$

where K_p and K_i are the control gain of proportion and integrator, respectively. The tuning objective of PI is shown in Fig.10(a) as follows:

$$\text{object} \begin{cases} G_d(j\omega_s)S_B(j\omega_s) < \gamma \\ |C_B(j\sqrt{2}\omega_s)G_d(j\sqrt{2}\omega_s)| < \eta \\ |T_C(\omega_c)| < \nu \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where $S_B(s) = 1/[1 + \bar{G}(s)G_d(s)C_B(s)]$ is the sensitive function, and $T_C(s) = \bar{G}(s)G_d(s)C_B(s)/[1 + \bar{G}(s)G_d(s)C_B(s)]$ is the complementary sensitivity function. The first objective represents the performances of vibration isolation at the resonant frequency, by reflecting the transmissibility of the closed-loop system. The second determines the performance of vibration isolation when the passive isolator starts working, to define the location of the roll-off frequency of the active isolator. The third denotes the bandwidth of the active vibration isolator, which is known as the complementary sensitivity to avoid high-frequency noise. To normalize (17), it can be transformed into an optimization problem for robust control:

$$\min_{K_i, K_p} \left\| \begin{bmatrix} W_S(s)S_B(s) \\ W_L(s)L_B(s) \\ W_C(s)T_C(s) \end{bmatrix} \right\|_n \quad (18)$$

where $L_B(s) = C_B(s)G_d(s)$ and n is the norm. Besides, the optimization problem (18) could be extended to designing other baseline tracking controllers, as shown in Fig.10(b).

Fig. 11. Experimental setup. (1) auxiliary mechanism, (2) VCM, (3) VCM drive module, (4) capacitive displacement sensors, (5) leaf spring, (6) PZT stacks, (7) preload spring, (8) AFM scanning head equivalent load, (9) FHSM, (10) PZT voltage amplifier, (11) dSPACE system.

Fig. 12. Experimental results of frequency response.

V. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the prototype system is established. A series of experimental tests, including performance tests of vibration isolation and closed-loop positioning are conducted, to verify the effectiveness and superiority of the modified compliant self-stabilization system with HAD.

A. Test setup

Based on our previous work, a prototype system is modified as shown in Fig.11. An auxiliary mechanism with a pair of cylindrical PZTs is set as the gantry and generates controllable and measurable vibration disturbances along vertical direction. A pair of PZT stacks (Pst150/7x7/20) forces the active vibration isolator to reject the vibration, and its displacement is measured by a set of sensors (NS-DCS10L-430F). The FHSM is fixed between the passive and active vibration isolator by designed brackets. The control implementation is achieved by the dSPACE rapid prototyping simulating system (DS-1007, dSPACE), and the control signal is amplified by the PZT voltage amplifier (E-500, PI).

B. Performances test of vibration isolation

The frequency response experiments of compliant self-stabilization system with and without precompression are conducted to verify the effectiveness of FHSM. A chirp signal with the frequency range from 0.1 Hz to 1000 Hz is utilized as the input signal. The experimental results of frequency

response are shown in Fig.12, which indicate that the resonant frequency is reduced to 8.9 Hz from 10.4 Hz (14.4 %), and the magnitude is suppressed to 18.8 μm from 23.89 μm (20.8 %). Furthermore, the resonant frequencies of the second mode of two cases are 55.3 Hz and 54.8 Hz respectively, while the second mode with precompression is further damped by FSHM. The experimental results generally match the FEA, thus the effectiveness of FHSM is verified.

Here, the vibration isolation performances of the system with HAD are verified, by testing under three cases, passive isolation with FHSM, hybrid isolation without ABD, and hybrid isolation with ABD. The FHSM is precompressed to dampen the system and reduce the resonant frequency, the VCM is worked as the ABD that is designed in Section IV. According to the superposition theorem of the linear system, and for highlighting the vibration isolation performances at one frequency, a set of sinusoidal waves with different frequencies are used as the disturbances. The fundamental frequency of the first disturbance is selected as 1 Hz since the disturbances are only canceled by the active vibration isolator. The second and third are set as 5 Hz and 10 Hz respectively, because these two frequencies are close to the identified resonant frequency. The remainder of disturbances are set as 50 Hz, 100 Hz, and 200 Hz, to verify the performances in high-frequency. The amplitude of disturbances is about $\pm 2 \mu\text{m}$ and the fundamental frequencies are located at the aforementioned points. When at 1 Hz as shown in Fig.13(a), it can be seen that the disturbance completely passes through the passive vibration isolator, and is suppressed by 94.8 % of vibration by the active vibration isolator, where the improvement of ABD is not obvious since the high control gain in low-frequency of active isolator. From Fig.13(b) and Fig.13(c), the vibrations are amplified by the passive vibration isolator with 155 % and 244 %, much lower than 585 % recorded in previous work without FHSM, thanks to the damping from FSHM. With the effort of HAD, the vibrations are suppressed by 94 % and 91 % in 5 Hz and 10 Hz respectively, keeping the AFM scanning head within in $\pm 0.12 \mu\text{m}$ and $\pm 0.18 \mu\text{m}$, where the improvement of ADB is achieved as 55.6 % and 40 % reduction, respectively. By Fig.13(d), Fig.13(e), and Fig.13(f), the vibrations are attenuated by the passive vibration isolator over 93.5 %, while the improvement of active unit is little since over the cross frequency. In addition, the vibration with frequencies from 200 Hz to 500 Hz can be also suppressed like Fig.13(e) and Fig.13(f). Additionally, limited by the resolution of the displacement sensor ($\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$), the actual residual vibrations are lower than $\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ in high-frequency ideally.

The overview of vibration isolation performances is plotted in Fig.14. By comparison, when only using passive vibration isolation, the resonant peak is suppressed 17 % by the FHSM, and the transmissibility rolls off below -20 dB before reaching 50 Hz. In other words, the proposed FHSM effectively dampens the resonant peak and still follows the inherent dynamics of the zero-stiffness mechanism in terms of amplification of excited signal at the resonant frequency. In terms of hybrid vibration isolation, when working without ABD, the transmissibility reaches -11 dB in the resonant region, and lower than -20 dB after 50 Hz. By introducing

Fig. 13. Vibration isolation performance test under vibration disturbances of the same amplitude and different frequencies. (a) 1 Hz. (b) 5 Hz. (c) 10 Hz. (d) 50 Hz. (e) 100 Hz. (f) 200 Hz.

Fig. 14. Comparison of the vibration isolation performance.

Fig. 15. Test result of positioning accuracy.

ABD, the transmissibility across working frequency is lower than -20 dB. With HAD, the positioning accuracy is kept within ± 0.18 μm in the resonant region, and ± 0.12 μm in other frequencies.

C. Performances test of closed-loop positioning

Besides vibration isolation, the positioning accuracy of the AFM scanning head is important for the application. To this end, a set of step signals with different amplitudes is used to simulate the environmental disturbances. The test result is displayed in Fig.15, where the disturbances are canceled with the overshoot within ± 0.3 μm . The steady-state error is kept within ± 0.1 μm , equal to the sensor noise, indicating that the attenuation ratio of the disturbances is achieved as 98 %.

D. Evaluation and discussion

To verify the effectiveness of the compliant self-stabilization system modified by the HAD strategy, several vibration isolators are compared with it, presented in [11], [12], [23]–[26], and previous work [4]. When assessing the performance evaluation of nanopositioning with vibration isolation function, typical quantities used to characterize the performance of vibration isolators are as follows: steady-state precision, load capacity, transmissibility (both in low and high frequencies), and working frequency. For a clear comparison with the modified system, the performances are listed in Table II, and the evaluations are as follows.

1) *Compared with passive strategy*: Considering the passive damping method based on negative stiffness in [12], it is

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE COMPARISONS OF SEVERAL VIBRATION ISOLATION STRATEGIES.

Ref.	Steady-state precision (μm)	Load capacity (kg)	Transmissibility (dB/Hz)	Working range (Hz)	Strategy
[4]	± 0.1	2.5	L: -0.1/10 H: -29.19/50	≤ 500	Hybrid
[11]	-	0.5	L: -1.22/5 H: -20/20	≤ 25	Hybrid
[12]	-	3.5	L: 8.8/5.66 H: -15.4/15	≤ 15	Passive
[23]	± 2	2	L: -3/2 H: -20/20	≤ 100	Active
[24]	± 8	3	L: 9.45/40 H: -19.2/130	≤ 150	Active
[25]	± 0.06	0.6	L: 22/0.08 H: -20/5	≤ 200	Active
[26]	± 2	50	L: -2/0.7 H: -20/3	≤ 100	Hybrid
This work	± 0.1	2.5	L: -20.92/10 H: -25.21/50	≤ 500	Hybrid

observed that the system offered a 3.5 kg payloads capacity, and low resonant frequency at 5.66 Hz benefited from the high-static–low-dynamic stiffness. However, the vibration is deteriorated low-frequency range. From this point of view, our work offers a high-efficiency vibration isolation in the low-frequency range, achieving over 90% reduction compared to a 238% increase in [12].

2) *Compared with active strategies:* Active methods face challenges in achieving high-performance of vibration isolation in the high-frequency range. The working range of [23]–[25] are all below 200 Hz, cannot meet the unique requirement of working range from 0 Hz to 500 Hz of the AFM system. In contrast, by the proposed HAD, the developed self-stabilization nanopositioning system is achieved as a vibration reduction ratio exceeding 90% across its working range from 0 Hz to 500 Hz, satisfying the unique requirements of the AFM system.

3) *Compared with hybrid strategies:* For hybrid approaches, simultaneously achieving high positioning accuracy, large working range, and heavy payloads is challenging. It is observed that the positioning error of [11], [26] are larger than $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$, while [11] only offers a load capacity of 0.6 kg. In terms of vibration isolation, the working range of [4], [11], [26] are all below 100 Hz, failing to effectively eliminate the vibration in resonant region. By the proposed HAD, the achieved 90% vibration reduction ratio across the working range (up to 500 Hz) can effectively meet the unique requirements of the AFM system.

In a word, the proposed HAD strategy enhances the performances of the developed system, ensuring high positioning accuracy ($\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$) and high load capacity (2.5 kg). This stability supports the steady-state position of the AFM scanning head. Notably, the system addresses crucial vibration isolation with HAD improvements, achieving a high vibration reduction ratio (over 90%) across the large working range (0 Hz to 500 Hz). The achievement provides powerful support for high-precision inspection equipment.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a hybrid add-on damping strategy for improving vibration isolator is proposed and validated. The main contributions can be summarized as follows:

- 1) A hybrid add-on damping strategy is developed to improve the vibration isolation of nanopositioning system from the viewpoint of existing device modification.
- 2) For hybrid add-on damping implementation, a flexure-based high-static-low-dynamics stiffness mechanism is designed for passive system pre-damping with reducing the deterioration of high-frequency transmissibility. Moreover, to further suppress the vibration in high-precision cases, an active band-width damper is developed to dampen the system within desired bandwidth.
- 3) A set of experiments were successfully performed, and the results indicate that the system achieved as a high vibration reduction ratio across its working range without sacrificing other performances.

Even so, the FHSM should be further optimized to suppress the vibration in the limited space, and will focus on studying high-performance damping control strategies to further reduce dependence on passive dampers.

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